

LIFE-FORM TRAITS IN *CRASSULA*

(A) Life-form classification of *Crassula*.

In red, the “traditional” Raunkiær’s life forms (abbreviations below).

<i>Crassula</i> life forms					
1 st LEVEL (Life-history strategies)		2 nd LEVEL (Growth forms)		3 rd LEVEL (Growth forms)	
1	Perennial (Monocarpic or polycarpic)	1.1	Shrub	1.1.1	Tall shrub (>50 cm) <i>nPh</i>
				1.1.2	Shrub (25–50 cm) <i>Ch</i>
				1.1.3	Dwarf shrub (0–25 cm) <i>Ch</i>
		1.2	Compact	1.2.1	Column <i>Ch</i>
				1.2.2	Rosette/Cushion <i>H</i>
		1.3	Geophyte <i>G</i>		
		1.4	Aquatic perennial <i>He/Hy</i>		
2	Annual <i>Th</i>	2.1	Terrestrial annual		
		2.2	Aquatic annual		

Abbreviations: *nPh*: nanophanerophyte, *Ch*: chamaephyte; *H*: hemicryptophyte; *G*: geophyte; *He*: helophyte; *Hy*: hydrophyte; *Th*: therophyte.

(B) Detailed description of life forms in *Crassula*.

1st LEVEL (LIFE-HISTORY STRATEGIES):

- **Polycarpic** (perennial): perennial plant flowering and fruiting many times.
- **Monocarpic** (perennial): perennial plant flowering and fruiting only once, and then dying.¹
- **Annual**: plant completing its life cycle within one year or one growing season.

2nd LEVEL (GROWTH FORMS):

- Perennial
 - **Shrub**: plant with visible internodes, usually profusely branched either from the base or along the main stem(s), with branches either erect or decumbent/procumbent.^{2,3}
 - **Compact**: plant with internodes extremely reduced, resulting in tightly arranged leaves.
 - **Geophyte**: plant which spends adverse season(s) in a resting state in underground organs.
 - **Aquatic perennial**: plant living partially or totally immersed in water, including muddy hollows and pools which may be seasonally dry.
- Annual
 - **Terrestrial annual**: same as **Shrub**, but annual life history.
 - **Aquatic annual**: same as **Aquatic perennial**, but annual life history.

3rd LEVEL (GROWTH FORMS):

- Shrub (Perennial)⁴
 - **Dwarf shrub**: shrub <25 cm tall.
 - **Shrub**: shrub 25-50 cm tall.
 - **Tall shrub**: shrub >50 cm tall.
- Compact (Perennial)
 - **Column**: plant characterised by a more or less erect columnar habit.
 - **Rosette/Cushion**: low-growing plant characterised by either spreading leaves arranged at ground level (i.e., rosette) or leaves supporting each other forming clumps (i.e., cushion).

¹ Upon floral induction, monocarpic plants devote all meristems to flower and fruit production, which later leads to whole plant senescence (see Amasino, 2009; Cotado and Munné-Bosch, 2020; Klimešová *et al.*, 2020). Even though a few highly branching, decumbent/procumbent *Crassula* taxa have often been described as monocarpic (e.g., *C. barklyi*, *C. pyramidalis*), observations in the wild suggest that these plants do not undergo a single flowering event and that only flowering branches enter senescence. Thus, they were not considered monocarpic in the current classification.

* *Crassula columnaris* ssp *prolifera* was misclassified as "monocarpic" in the paper but has been corrected to "polycarpic" (see Excel file) based on observations in the wild showing extensive branching from the base.

² All perennial species with visible internodes fall in this category and are considered "shrubs" *sensu lato*, despite some of them not becoming significantly woody. Woodiness is not an easy trait to measure (see Rowe and Paul-Victor, 2012; Carlquist, 2013) and is quite variable within *Crassula* taxa, so the distinction between "shrub" and "herb" is not practical.

³ Some decumbent/procumbent *Crassula* taxa may resemble compact forms at first glance (e.g., *C. pubescens*, *C. swaziensis*), but internodes are clearly visible upon closer examination.

⁴ Trait values were allocated based on descriptions in the literature; therefore, this classification might not be very robust.

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